

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LONG DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	09	23	Belém	S 01	26.910	W 048	30.047
End	2021	10	09	Salvador de Bahía	S 12	58.304	W 038	30.960

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

This leg was dedicated to get a deeper understanding of how the Amazon River influences the Atlantic Microbiome, as well as to characterize the plastic transported by the river to the Ocean, and the plastisphere. We performed three stations (043, 044, 045). The stations 043 and 044 were done in the system of River Pará and the 045 was done in the NBC, upstream of the Amazon plume.

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin Hertau
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves Tournon
3	CREW - Mecano	Loic Caudan
4	CREW - Deck	David Monmarche
5	CREW - Deck	Francois Aurat
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie Bin
7	CREW - Media	Maeva Bardy
8	GUEST - Artist	-
9	GUEST - Observer	Guilherme Cajueiro
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Alison Chase (AC)
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Helena Cruz de Carvalho (HCC)
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Douglas Couet (DC)
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Alessandra Gomez (AG)
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Paula Huber (PH)

SAMPLING STRATEGY & ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

Station 043 was done close to the city of Belém in the Baía Guarajá (where the river Guamá meets the river Acará, Figure 1). The sampling was performed during the High - Low tide cycle (ebb). Due to the difficulties in the previous river stations (040 from leg5 and 041 from leg6) due to the high concentrations of particles in suspension, we adapted some protocols and sampling strategy.

Station 044 was done in the River Tocantins (Figure 1) as a reference of less impacted waters, compared with 043. As with 043 the sampling was performed during the High - Low tide cycle (ebb), and we also had to adapt some protocols and sampling strategies due to the particles in suspension.

Station 045 was done in the North Brazilian Current upstream of the Amazon plume (Figure 1) as a reference for “no surface freshwater” condition. The sampling was performed in two days at: surface, 2 epipelagic depths and 2 mesopelagic depths.

Figure 1. Sampling stations (043, 044 & 045) location performed during the leg 7 (MM-Belém-Salvador de Bahia). A) Chlorophyl; B) Sea Surface Salinity; C) Sea Surface Height. Maps provided by Lea Olivier (LOCEAN-IPSL)

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

The Amazon River is the world's largest river and discharges a tremendous amount of freshwater into the Atlantic Ocean generating an extensive surface plume. This impacts not only all the communities inhabiting it, but also in the global biogeochemical cycles.

During two months we navigated the Amazon River waters and its plume with the main aim to increase our knowledge on how the river affects the Atlantic Microbiome. On board Tara, we moved from the blue ocean, through emerald-green waters of the plume, to the immense brown-waters of the Amazon River.

If I should describe in a few words these legs, I would say: extremely dynamic and innovative sampling campaign.

We took a huge amount of samples which will allow us to study the surface and deep microbiome, and the plastisphere, combining cutting-edge molecular and microscopy techniques.

Each sampling station was particular in its challenges, difficulties, and wonderfulness. And we should adapt to this dynamic, being part of the system, in order to better understand it. Thus, as young researchers on board, the Mission Microbiome in the Amazon Plume led us to improve not only our technical skills, but also our adaptability and organizational capabilities.

I would like to emphasize that the success of these legs was possible thanks to the enthusiastic participation and constant interaction between the scientists on board and the crew personnel, as well as with researchers on land. Personally, this expedition was an amazing experience and it is a pleasure to be part of this team.

SCP50	petri-slide	5											
F200	250-mL-bottle		10										
E200	15-mL-falcon							10					
S200	5-mL-cryotube									10			
S200-L	5-mL-falcon						10						
PM-HG200	Zip-lock	10											
MB200	4-mL-Vial						10						
CP200	petri-slide	10											
F680	250-mL-bottle		3										
F2000	250-mL-bottle		4										
E680	15-mL-falcon							3					
S680-L	MULTIPLATES								3				
E2000	15-mL-falcon							5					
AI	petri-slide	42											
AS	2-mL-cryotube											42	
AF	Zip-lock						42						
SP300	2-mL-cryotube											27	
MP300	2-mL-cryotube						5						
CP300	petri-slide	13											
TOC	30-mL-bottle								6				
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube											3	
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube											3	
S025-L	15-mL-falcon							15					
S520-L	5-mL-falcon						15						
FM5	5-mL-falcon				30								
MTE-BP	125-mL Bottle			2									
	TOTAL	154	47	46	50	0	50	180	105	9	168	140	120